

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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CHARACTER ACCENTUATION IN ADOLESCENCE

Abdullayeva Risolat Eshangul qizi

Termez State University

Faculty of Social Sciences

Applied Psychology III course student

risolatabdullayeva993@gmail.com

Annotation: this article covers the character traits, types and classification experienced by adolescents. The article provides important recommendations to parents.

Keyword: adolescence, parent, teacher, character, classification, person, society, period, family.

Bringing the new generation to adulthood, the formation of the personality of citizens who meet the requirements of society, who will help him to fulfill the tasks set before him, has been the highest goal of each system. The improvement of the system of gradual formation of human personality in our republic is another vivid evidence of our opinion. The formation of methods of attitude of children corresponding to different age periods about their young psychological characteristics, the observance of their laws, countless opinions were expressed even during the period of the former regime of shuralar, countless R & D work was carried out. It should be recognized that, although bitter, the said thoughts did not cause a slightest shock to the scientific value of the studies carried out, the ideological demand of that time for the formation of members of an obedient, believing society did not give a full chance to apply these works to practice. Now the times have changed, the times have changed, the political, economic, social status of our Republic has changed. We have taken the path of integration. In the process of complex political, economic relations, there was a need for members of society who could take an unbiased direction, think independently, react independently. In our republic, the process of forming the personality of citizens of a new society has begun, which can meet these requirements on a large scale. "However, in a holistic assessment, we must admit that the activities we have carried out over the past period are not giving the results that life demands today. First of all, it should

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be noted that we have not fully recovered from the ideological views and sarqits inherent in the educational system left over from the Old, Salty times". Each age period is of particular importance in the formation of a person's personality. But there are also periods of special importance within these periods, one of which is adolescence. The scientific literature from this period contains the terms "transitional period", "crisis period", "difficult period", all of which can be said to correctly reflect the characteristics of this period.

The most basic feature of adolescence is characterized by the intensity of two developments: psychic and physical or, in other words, psychic and somatic processes. Each of us observed in our children and educators such clearly visible, sharply manifested forms of behavior that are characteristic of this very period, such as serfdom, rudeness, giving attention to oneself beyond the right.

Character accentuation-K. Being a concept introduced by Leongard, the character is an example of the vivid expressiveness of some qualities. Knowledge of character accentuacy is necessary in the form of an individual approach to adolescents, vocational guidance. Self – assessment-self-assessment as a result of self-comparison and reflection of an individual with others is complex and variable, and occupies a large place in the structure of the individual.

On the basis of various classifications, the following main types of character accentuation are distinguished:

1. Cycloid-alternates in different periods of phases of good and bad mood stand.
2. Hypertim-a constant uplifting mood, sticking to several jobs in one way high psychic activity with a tendency and thirst for activity, starting work not to end.
3. Labilp is a sudden change in mood, depending on the situation.
4. Asthenic-frequent exhaustion, irritability, depression and predisposition to hypochondria (depression - mental crunch, hypochondria-panic).
5. Censitive-high tactility, impotence, personal incompleteness increased sense.
6. Psychasthenic - high anxiety, badgumony, juxtaposition, constant doubt and meditation, a tendency to self-analysis, ritual actions and obsession trend.

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7. Schizoid-separation from others, isolation, interversion, sympathy the absence and emotional contacts are manifested in the difficulty of installation emotional coldness, lack of intuition in the process of communication.

8. Epileptoid - (baozan with elements of cruelty) rabies and with the accumulation of aggression, which manifests itself in the form of the appearance of cancer irritable-a tendency to a sad mood, quarrels, flexibility of thinking, pedantism to the extent of hypocrisy (past formalism).

9. Incontinence (parangoyal) - high scurvy and disease arasism at the level, the constancy of negative effects, the desire for superiority, etc high quarrels as a result of not accepting their thoughts.

10. Demonstrative (hysteroid) - "sick" when the need for recognition is not satisfied take up", manmanism, characterized by a penchant for shaky things, to himself loneliness, fantasy, and used to attract attention mugambirlik, suppressing facts and phenomena that are unpleasant for the subject trend.

11. Dysthymia is the predominance of depressed mood, predisposition to depression, life give in to the sad and sad sides.

12. Unstable - a tendency to be relieved by the influence of those around him, always new installation, searching for circles, easily installing a contact with a superficial character get.

13. Conformal is an extra-hade dependence on the opinions of others, and subordination, lack of criticality and initiative, conservatism inclination.

As mentioned above character accentuation of adolescence

indispensable sign. each teenager, without exception, manifests one or more of these characteristics in himself. But in the next stages, these properties should be smoothed out. Only in psychogenic situations of constant influence are these characteristics can become stronger. And such situations sometimes arise because of US adults, educators, parents. Sometimes adults perceive such cases of adolescents as indiscipline, deliberate indecency, as a result of psychological illiteracy, due to their ignorance of the laws of psychic and somatic development. Teachers who have a negative "I concept", on the other hand, have the main goal of " curbing " children in general. The resulting character they are responsible for the subsequent growth of their accentuation into the field of psychopath.

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We adults can easily, without mental strain, adapt to children with our own flexible character traits. It is for this teenager that in a difficult period of "personality me", "sexual" formation, with our patience, kindness, we can help them relax from mental tension, show ways to sublimate the natural sexual and aggressive inclinations in them.

The role of upbringing and self-education in the growth of character is great. Growing up the character of the coming young generation is brought up, first of all, in the family and at school. A large responsible task in raising the character of children falls on parents, teachers and kindergarten educators. In character education, the educator must be well aware of the positive and negative aspects of the child's temperament. Character training consists, among other things, of cultivating the positive aspects of temperament, losing its negative aspects and replacing these negative aspects with the positive emotions of the character. In order to lose the negative side of the character, to bring up the positive side, it is necessary to teach the educator to control his own temperament. being able to control one's own temperament is a positive feeling of character.

How parents can help a teenager grow: 1. Make your home as comfortable and stable as possible 2. A subtle approach to the upbringing of a teenager and support the activities of any creative group. 2. A subtle approach to the upbringing of a teenager and support the activities of any creative group. 3. Don't blame him for his desire to grow up, especially the need to part with you. 3. Don't blame him for his desire to grow up, especially the need to part with you. 4. Set the most democratic rules in the family. 5. Listen to the opinion and point of view of the teenager. The transitional period is a period of confusion. Your perception of his emotions will help reduce the level of inner disorder of the teenager. 5. Listen to the opinion and point of view of the teenager. The transitional period is a period of confusion. Your perception of his emotions will help reduce the level of inner disorder of the teenager. 6. A teenager needs recognition and a sense of competence. 7. Consider the need for him to remain silent for a while. Set and follow the Basic Rules for what living with a teenager can be regulated. Although teenagers talk about freedom, in reality they want to know where the boundaries are, and feel uncomfortable

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and restless in the complete absence of restrictions. Drawing a line is one of the manifestations of love.

Each child should be assigned some kind of responsibility - washing dishes, cleaning, etc. Avoid making rules that are difficult to implement. There is depression when trying to break the rules or go around them. Set and follow the Basic Rules for what can be regulated. Although teenagers talk about freedom, in reality they want to know where the boundaries are, and feel uncomfortable and restless in the complete absence of restrictions. Drawing a line is one of the manifestations of love. Each child should be assigned some kind of responsibility - washing dishes, cleaning, etc. Avoid making rules that are difficult to implement. There is depression when trying to break the rules or go around them. Give your teenager the opportunity to participate in family discussions. This does not mean involving him in everything. But recognize his right to vote in matters concerning the whole family. Do you need to build a porch or buy a trailer? You had the opportunity to get a job in another city; how does he react to the movement? If the child does not have the opportunity to enjoy family benefits, it is difficult to expect him to respect family responsibility. Give your teenager the opportunity to participate in family discussions. This does not mean involving him in everything. But recognize his right to vote in matters concerning the whole family. Do you need to build a porch or buy a trailer? You had the opportunity to get a job in another city; how does he react to the movement? If the child does not have the opportunity to enjoy family benefits, it is difficult to expect him to respect family responsibility. Treat your child as a personal person - this is not the embodiment or expansion of your expectations. You can advise and approve, but you cannot control his ship. Treat your child as a personal person - this is not the embodiment or expansion of your expectations. You can advise and approve, but you cannot control his ship.

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